

Fabrication of Eco-Friendly Electric Tricycles with Solar Panels for Handicapped Person

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Abstract. Solar energy is energy in the form of rays and heat from the sun. This energy can be harnessed by using a series of technologies such as solar panels. Solar panels are devices that consist of solar cells that convert light into electrical energy. The use of solar panels for battery charging on electric tricycles is the topic of this research. The process of developing an electric tricycle with solar power consists of several stages, starting from the preparation of the tricycle, the development design, the manufacture of the solar panel frame and holder, to the assembly and testing process. The result of this research is an electric tricycle uses a 48 Volt with 2 units solar panel 100 Wp, 7.2 Ah battery with a charging time of 1 hours 22 minutes, using a 350 Watt Brushless DC motor. The maximum speed of an electric tricycle with solar panels is as expected, which is a distance range of 45 km and a load of 120 kg (with person).

Keywords: Tricycle, solar panel, Brushless DC motor, Battery

INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles, which use 100% electric power, use electric motors instead of an internal combustion engine to provide motive force. Solar-powered vehicles (SPVs) use photovoltaic (PV) cells to convert sunlight into electricity. The electricity goes either directly to an electric motor powering the vehicle, or to a special storage battery. PV cells produce electricity only when the sun is shining. Without sunlight, a solar powered car depends on electricity stored in its batteries.[1][2]

Mobility plays a vital role in social life of a human being. For that sake different vehicle have been developed but almost all of them produced for normal person. As far as a physically handicapped person is concerned, there are limited vehicles are available for personal use. Vehicles for a disabled person either of custom made or conventional hand operated cycle. They meant to fulfill basic functional need and seldom put the emphasis on other factors. Most of listed options have poor aesthetics or cost issues. Even though Previous options has given different design which are sophisticated but failed to consider many factors like weight, cost, simplicity, emission and operational cost.[3][4]

The basic tricycle is a three wheeled design for disabled person. They use only one hand to steer and other to rotate the pedal. Main content of the tricycle is solar panel, Brushless DC motor controller and battery. The power transmission of solar tricycle is simple. World is moving towards automation where human effort decreased. But physically challenged people left challenged. By using solar energy to obtain power required for powering the automobile design various conclusive effects. Renewable energy powered by vehicles or other appliances bring down Global warming and depletion of non-renewable sources. Hence in this paper we discuss about solar cycle for physically challenge people using solar energy for cycle is an eco-friendly approach. It decreases the usage of conventional fuels which decreases pollution, solar tricycle is design to achieve a speed of 25-30 Kmph.[5][6][7]

METHODS

On body we fixed seat, battery support and panel supporting rods. For solar panel, battery and seat support we used angular rods. Total weight of the loaded solar tricycle (with a person) is 120 kg. As a transport for the physically disabled people the overall safety, stability, reliability, control, comforts etc. are a very much important and taken in to consideration while designing it. However, the general points of consideration during the designing of the solar three-wheeler are: simplicity, strength, stability, safety, corrosion and wear, weight, size, flexibility, ease of control, modularity, efficient extraction of solar energy, effective use of solar energy and energy storage, all terrain tires for all terrain traffic ability.[8][9][10]

Figure 1. Proposed Design of the Solar Tricycle

Advantages :

- Solar energy creates absolutely no pollution. This is perhaps the most important advantage that makes solar energy so much more practical than fuel.
- Solar panels and solar lighting may seem quite expensive when you first purchase it, but in the long run you will find yourself saving quite a great deal of money. After all, it does not cost anything to harness the power of the sun. Unfortunately, paying for oil is an expensive prospect and the cost is still rising consistently.
- It will reduce the efforts of the handicapped person.
- It is very cheap as compared to the other motorized vehicles, for handicapped person, in the market.

Applications :

- The main application of the project is to provide a tricycle which required less or no effort to ride.
- The solar tricycle is ecofriendly and thus causes no pollution.
- Covers more distance due to the power of the solar energy.
- It is cheap, simple, and low maintenance.

Specifications :

Specification of The Proposed Tricycle Components:

- Solar panel: 100 Wp
- Brushless DC motor: 48 Volt, Power rating is 350 W
- Battery: 48 Volt, 7.2 Ah
- Maximum load capacity: 120 kg.

The block diagram of (Figure 1) the solar power system used in the project gives the overall working structure of the system. Initially the solar panel is placed on the top of the tricycle, which converts the solar energy to electrical energy, is connected to the battery in order to charge it with the help of a charge controller, the charge controller converts the fluctuating/pulsating flow of electric charge into constant flow of electric charge which can be supplied to the battery to charge it. Now, the battery supplies the required amount of power to the DC motor, which is connected to the axle of the wheel. A throttle is provided to control or maintain the speed of the tricycle.[11][12][13]

Consideration & Calculations:

The total weight of the tricycle is 120 kg (including person).

1) Motor :

How much power do we need in watts?

Power (watts) = Total weight x g x speed x gradient

Total weight = 120 kg

Speed = 25 kmph = $25 \times \frac{5}{18}$ m/s

Gradient = slope (assume 3%)

Power = $120 \times 9.81 \times 25 \times \frac{5}{18} \times .03 = 245.25$ watt Therefore power required approximately is 250 watt. Thus a 24 Volt, 250 W motor will be enough for tricycle

2) Battery :

System voltage 48 Volt,

Load current = $\frac{350\text{w}}{48\text{v}} = 7.29$ A Estimate 2 hours of tricycle running per day Load current = $2 \times 7.29 \times 1.2 = 18$ Ah/day Assume 17% overall losses, Size of battery = $25 \times 1.2 = 30$ Ah/day Energy required for 350 W motor = $30 \text{ Ah} \times 48 \text{ V} = 1440$ Ah/day. Therefore 30 Ah/day, 48 Volt power is required for the system which can be supplied with the help of two 48 Volt batteries of 30 Ah/day.

3) Solar Panel :

Commercially available single solar cells normally have the dimensions of 770 x 540 x 30 mm. Here, in the module, 36 cells are connected (in series) together so that in all operating conditions a PV module which is the required to charge a 48 V battery.[14][15]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Testing of Solar Panel Electric Bike Charging This electric bicycle battery charging test aims to determine whether the solar panel electric bicycle battery charging process is going well and as expected. Testing the battery charging from solar panels do during the sun is shining to get maximum charging time.

Measurement of Battery Charging Time The electric bike is designed using 4 unit's battery with a capacity of 12V/7.2 Ah each. The battery is then assembled in a series that produces 48V/7.2 Ah capacity. The measurement of battery charging time is shown in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1. Measurement of Battery Charging Time

No	Battery Charging	Initial Battery	Charging Time, Beginning and End	Time to Full Battery Charging	Current (Ampere)	Explanation
1	Solar Panel	Low Battery	08.00 – 18.10	2 hours 22 minutes	1.1 A	Sun is shining
2	Solar Panel	Low Battery	08.00 – 13.10	7 hours 27 minutes	0.5 A	Cloudy
3	Electricity Power (PLN)	Low Battery	12.30 – 18.30	15 hours 3 minutes	1.8 A	

First test on Monday, January 02, 2023, 08:00-18.10 when the sun is shining. The second test was on Thursday, January 05, 2023, 08.00–13.10 when in cloudy conditions. Charging uses two solar panels connected in series with a total capacity of 100 Wp. The use of a 100 Wp solar panel to keep the battery from overcharging for long life. The weight of two units of solar panels 100 Wp can be supported by an electric tricycle. The solar panel is installed horizontally on the tricycle to keep the tricycle stable while driving. The process of charging the battery must be observed at all times. Before charging the battery, the indicator must show that the battery is empty so that when making measurements an accurate time is obtained. Charging the battery from the solar panel goes well with the voltage and current of the solar panel, namely 48V / 7.2A with a charging time of 2 hours 22 minutes.

Measurement of Speed and Distance of Electric Tricycles Testing an electric bicycle with a weight of 50 kg and a load mass (person) of 50 kg, 67 kg, and 70 kg. The purpose of this test is to determine the maximum speed that can be achieved by an electric tricycle. The object under study is the travel time and the distance traveled. This test was carried out along Campus ITSNU Pasuruan Street. Measurement of the speed and distance traveled by an electric tricycle is carried out using the digital speedometer hand-steer. Measurement of the speed and distance traveled by an electric tricycle is shown in Table 2 as follows:

Table 2. Measurement of Speed and Distance of Electric Tricycles

No	Initial Battery	Current (Ampere)	Bike Weight (Kg)	Rider Weight (kg)	Maximum Speed (Km/hour)	Distance (Km)	Time (Minutes)
1	Full Battery	5.5	50	50	25	19	57
2	Full Battery	6.9	50	67	25	17	51
3	Full Battery	8.4	50	70	25	14	42

The first test was conducted on Monday, January 02, 2023, 08:00-18.10, with a total mass of 100 Kg. The second test was conducted on Thursday, January 05, 2023, 08.00–13.10, with a total mass of 117 Kg. The third test was carried out on Friday, January 06, 2023, 12.30–18.30 with a total mass of 120 kg. The maximum speed of the solar panel electric tricycle is as expected, which is 25 km/hour with an average distance of 17 km. Distance and travel time are affected by the weight of the rider. The average speed, maximum speed, and distance traveled by an electric tricycle can be seen on the screen display of the speedometer. Measuring the distance traveled by an electric tricycle is done by riding an electric tricycle until the indicator shows the condition of the battery is completely empty.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the discussion and testing of electric tricycles with solar panel, conclusions can be drawn including:

1. Objective of the study was to design an eco-friendly vehicle which will be affordable to poor handicapped person.
2. Tricycle has been fabricated and tested successfully.
3. Different parameters like running range, cost per kilometer, Discharge time of battery has been measured with actual running condition and it delivered better results.
4. We mitigated problems faced by previously designed model.
5. The maximum speed of an electric bicycle with solar panels is as expected, which is 25 km/hour with a distance of 17 km.

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